

“Just Transition” Visions: An Analysis of the Perception of the Belgian Actors

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Working paper

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1. Introduction

The “just transition” is a large concept referring mainly to the quite recent claim to take social aspects into account in the global environmental transition. It arises from the observations that a transition process inevitably includes positive impacts - reason why the transition is initiated - as well as negative ones that have to be avoided or smoothed (Henry, et al., 2020). The concept first emerged in the US labor movement (CSIS & CIF, 2020) and has progressively acquired a broad range of understandings, definitions and uses which have been extensively discussed in the academic literature (Wang & Lo, 2021). The concept has also gained importance in international fora such as the International Labour Organization (ILO) and its guiding principles for a just transition published in 2015, the EU with the Green Deal pillar of “leaving no one behind” or the UNFCCC processes with the adoption of the “Solidarity and Just Transitions Silesia Declaration” at the COP24 meeting in Poland (Jenkins, et al., 2020).

There is no universal definition of the concept and, considering that the “just transition” process involves many actors whose values, points of view and interests diverge, the term “just” in “just transition” has different meanings depending on which “superior common principle” it is referred to (Didier, 2020). Ideal-typical approaches of just transitions can therefore “range from those that preserve the existing political and economic status quo to those that envision significantly different futures” (UNRISD, 2018).

Besides providing a “structured and operationalized” definition of a “just transition” based on identified visions (Bauler, et al., 2021) and exploring the justice issues associated to ecological transitions in Belgium, it is essential to comprehend the visions of “just transition” that exist in Belgium and to understand this plurality of perspectives.

The main objective of the present analysis is therefore to identify and map the visions of “just transition” in Belgium. This analysis aims at sketching contrasting visions of “just transition” in Belgium and at identifying the actors who support these visions as well as the areas of consensus and debate on the question.

With that aim in mind, we have carried out a survey among Belgian actors concerned by the “just transition” based on Q methodology. This has allowed us to outline three “ideal-typical visions” of a just transition by Belgian actors. These visions are complemented with a fourth vision that has been identified through the analysis of secondary sources.

The following section presents the Q survey method and how we conducted it. Section 3 displays the results of the Q survey, the description of the three “ideal-typical visions” and presents the fourth vision. Section 4 includes a discussion of these results and the conclusion.

2. Methodology

In this section, we will firstly present the Q methodology (see 2.1), then present how we conducted the Q survey and its different steps (see 2.2). Finally, we will explain the reasons which led us to the identification of a fourth ideal-typical vision (see 2.3). We chose the Q methodology because it is well-suited to apprehend in a structured way the plurality of perceptions that exist around controversial issues.

2.1. Presentation of the Q methodology

The Q methodology is a survey method based on statistical analysis which allows one to understand the variety of perceptions on a given subject through the definition of “typical ideal discourses” (see Watts & Stenner, 2005).

There are several steps needed to conduct a Q methodology. Preliminary steps consist of constructing the **Q sample** (see 2.2.1) by identifying the different stakeholders directly involved in or gravitating around the studied topic, and to whom the survey will be sent.

Another preliminary step consists of identifying the discourses to study in order to establish the **Q set** (see 2.2.2) through the analysis of grey or academic literature (articles, reports, websites, flyers, etc.) or several face-to-face interviews. From this discourse analysis, the research team will indeed select and formulate a broad range of statements (the Q set) covering their main positions, interpretations, practices, understandings, or potential disagreements related, in this specific case, to the concept of “just transition”.

Subsequently, the survey itself aims at collecting field data (**Q sorts**) through an **online questionnaire** (see 2.2.3) **or through interviews** with the participants. In both cases, the participants start by answering **introductory questions** and then sort the statements of the Q set across each other in a ranking grid before answering a post-sorting questionnaire where they can explain the reasons for their ranking and, more specifically, why they put certain statements in the extreme positive or negative position in the ranking grid.

The obtained Q sorts are then analyzed (see 2.2.4) through a **Principal Component Analysis (PCA)** which aims at identifying different “factors”, with each factor corresponding to an “ideal-typical version” of a vision shared by a group of participants.

Finally, the obtained factors are described and analyzed based on the typical Q-sorts and the answers to the post-sorting questionnaire.

2.2 Conduct of the Q survey

The following section presents in more detail the four phases of the Q survey we conducted: the construction of the sample (Q sample), the formulation of the items (Q set), the data collection and the data analysis.

2.2.1 Construction of the sample (Q sample)

The sample of persons invited to participate in the Q survey (Q sample) included the actors involved in the just transition in Belgium. These actors were identified through a purposive sampling approach. We started from the list of civil society actors identified by the Office of Minister Khattabi to participate in the “Forum for a just transition”. This list has been completed to cover all possible points of view on the just transition in Belgium and consists of representatives of civil society organizations (NGOs, Advisory councils, Trade unions, Business federations, etc.), administrations, political authorities, citizen movements and researchers. The final list comprised 295 people.

31 people completed the survey and sent their responses, among which 29 people completed the Q survey. The Q sample therefore is composed of:

- **fourteen people working for an administration or another public organization (ADM)** and which are active in the fields of sustainable development, climate mitigation and adaptation, labour market, social and circular economy, taxation and finance, fight against poverty and social energy
- **six people working for a trade union (TRU)**
- **five people working for an NGO (NGO)** and which are active in the fields of political ecology, environmental and climate mitigation policies, just transition and climate justice
- **two people involved in a citizen movement (CIT)** and which are active in the fields of climate justice and sustainable consumption
- **two people involved in other types of organizations (OTH)**

Category of actors	Total
Administration and other public administrations (ADM)	14
Trade Unions (TRU)	6
Non-governmental organizations (NGO)	5
Citizen movements (CIT)	2
Other types or organizations (OTH)	2
Total	29

Table 1 – Category of actors

It is worth noting that, although we contacted 70 business federations, we only received two responses from this type of actor to the questions of the survey. These two responses took the form of emails in which they described their vision of a just transition as well as the statements which they want to put forward as most representative of their vision of a just transition. As a result, as explained in section 2.3, we decided to analyze these responses as well as secondary sources to identify their vision of a just transition,

2.2.2 Formulation of the items (Q set)

With a view to formulate the set of items supposed to cover all possible discourses on just transition in Belgium (Q set), we have carried out a documentary research and exploratory interviews.

The documentary research aimed to collect and analyze documents on “just transition” developed by various civil society actors (employers, trade unions, NGOs, etc.), political parties, institutional actors and academics in order to comprehend their vision of just transition. We searched for mentions of “just transition” in different types of sources, including policy plans and legislations; advisory councils’ notices; press articles; as well as reports, position paper, communications, recommendations and websites from various actors concerned by just transition. Although we mainly focused on documents produced by Belgian actors, we also considered some key documents developed at the European and international level. The collected documents were analyzed through an analytical framework aimed at comprehending different dimensions of the visions of “just transition” developed. This analytical framework as well as the list of documents analyzed is presented in the appendix (see Appendix 1 and 2). On this basis, we have formulated a first set of items.

This set of items was consolidated based on 6 exploratory interviews conducted with representatives of the different social groups and institutions concerned with “just transition” in Belgium:

Industries with high GHG emissions	<i>FEBELIEC</i>
Companies	<i>FEB</i>
Consumers	<i>AB-REOC</i>
People living in unfavorable socio-economic conditions	<i>Interfederal Service for the Fight against Poverty</i>
Civil society	<i>Coalition Climat</i>
Citizen Movement	<i>Extinction Rebellion</i>

Table 2 – Actors consulted for the exploratory interviews

The interview guide is presented in the appendix (Annex 3).

The documentary research and the exploratory interviews led to the formulation of 89 statements from which we have selected 39. The final set of items is shown below:

1	Only the justice issues associated to the climate problem should be considered as the scope of just transition
2	The justice issues associated to the climate problem, but also to other ecological issues (ex.: biodiversity loss, pollution...) should be considered within the scope of just transition
3	Justice in the distribution of cost and benefits of ecological transitions policies (ex.: carbon tax, energy subsidies...) should be considered within the scope of just transition
4	Justice in the distribution of the impacts (ex.: heat waves, floodings...) of ecological problems should be considered within the scope of just transition
5	Just transition should target vulnerable territories (ex.: regions dependent on fossil fuels, countries in the South...)

6	Just transition should target vulnerable companies (ex.: fossil fuel industries)
7	Just transition should target vulnerable workers (ex.: fossil fuel industries workers)
8	Just transition should target vulnerable social groups (ex.: low-income households, people with health concerns, people living in rural areas, women, elderly people...)
9	Just transition should target vulnerable generations (ex.: future generations)
10	Just transition should target vulnerable non-humans (ex.: animals, plants...)
11	The “just” in “just transition” should mean not increasing existing inequalities
12	The “just” in “just transition” should mean reducing existing inequalities
13	The “just” in “just transition” should mean eradicating poverty
14	The “just” in “just transition” should mean ensuring access to fundamental rights for all
15	The “just” in “just transition” should mean ensuring quality and decent jobs for all
16	The “just” in “just transition” should mean tackling systemic forms of oppression associated to race, gender, class and/or species
17	The “just” in “just transition” should mean reducing existing power imbalance
18	The “just” in “just transition” should mean deepening and reinforcing democracy
19	Just transition requires prioritizing ecological and/or social objectives over economic growth
20	Just transition requires promoting sustainable social innovations based on solidarity (ex.: car sharing, agricultural cooperatives, energy communities, repair cafés...)
21	Just transition requires investing in the research and development of sustainable technologies
22	Just transition requires phasing-out, as of now, industries, technologies, business models and practices that raise systemic sustainability issues (ex.: fossil fuel extraction, polluting vehicles...)
23	Just transition involves compensating workers affected by closures or downsizing of industries
24	Just transition requires investing in reskilling workers
25	Just transition requires investing in sustainable and job-rich sectors
26	Just transition requires investing in the diversification of local economies
27	Just transition requires ensuring the competitiveness of Belgian companies at the European and/or global levels

28	Just transition requires ensuring the security of supply in terms of energy and materials
29	Just transition requires making sustainable alternatives accessible to disadvantaged social groups
30	Just transition requires taxing large companies more and to redistribute the benefit to households
31	Just transition requires developing a fair ecological taxation
32	Just transition requires developing a social security that recognizes ecological transitions and environmental degradation as social risks that need to be mutualized
33	Just transition requires assisting the recovery of ecosystems that has been degraded, damaged, or destroyed people in Belgium and/or elsewhere in the world
34	Just transition requires compensating for the ecological loss and damage caused to people in Belgium and/or elsewhere in the world
35	Just transition requires developing rights for non-human (animals, plants...)
36	Just transition requires meaningful participation, including that of vulnerable groups. Meaningful participation implies involvement that affords some degree of influence in the decision-making process.
37	Just transition requires tackling existing unequal power relations that afford varying levels of influence in decision-making processes
38	Just transition should be achieved within the existing political and economic systems
39	Just transition requires to overhaul the existing political and/or economic systems

Table 3 – The final Q set with the 39 statements

2.2.3 Data collection

We used the [QMethodSoftware](#) to construct the online questionnaire and to collect the answers of the participants. This online questionnaire consisted of various parts:

- Introductory questions (see below)
- Pre-sorting the statements (where the participants indicated whether they agreed or disagreed with the 39 statements)
- The Q survey (where the participants were invited to classify the previously developed items in a ranking grid according to how representative they found the statements of their vision of just transition)
- Concluding questions (post-sort questionnaire, see below)

2.2.3.1 Introductory Survey

Before starting the ranking, the participants were invited to complete an introductory survey, which included the following questions:

2.2.3.3 Post-sorting questionnaire

Finally, the participants were invited to answer questions in a post-sorting questionnaire where they were able to explain their ranking of the statements and why they put certain statements in the extreme positive or negative position in the ranking grid.

This survey included the following questions:

Questions in the post-sorting questionnaire
Could you please explain why you strongly agree or disagree with the statements to which you gave an extreme score (+3 and -3) (You can answer in EN, FR or NL)
Are there important elements of your vision of “just transition” that you have not found in the statements you have classified (You can answer in EN, FR or NL)
In your opinion, what are the relevant indicators to monitor and evaluate progress in “just transition” (You can answer in EN, FR or NL)
In your opinion, who should be involved in these monitoring and evaluation processes? (You can answer in EN, FR or NL)
Would you like to add something ? (You can answer in EN, FR or NL)

Table 5 – Questions in the post-sorting questionnaire

2.2.4 Data analysis

We used the [Ken-Q Analysis](#) software to analyze the “Q sorts” obtained during the survey.

The analysis aims to identify “factors” based on a principal component analysis (PCA) followed by a factor rotation. A factor corresponds to a typical Q sort and is therefore a particular point of view shared by several participants. The factor rotation involves maximizing the contributions of the selected factors (see section 2.2.4.1 Principal Component Analysis) to the explanations of the variance.

2.2.4.1 Principal Component Analysis

After encoding the data, a principal component analysis (PCA) was conducted to study the intercorrelations between the Q-sorts. The first step of the PCA provides the matrix of the correlations between the Q-sorts (see Annex 4). A perfect positive correlation between two Q-sorts is equal to 100 and a perfect negative correlation is equal to -100. A correlation between two Q-sorts is considered significant when it is superior to 38 or 48¹.

Based on the matrix of correlations between Q-sorts, the PCA extracted eight factors. The values in the matrix crossing those factors with the Q sorts (see Annex 4) represent the correlation between the factors and the Q sort. A perfect positive correlation equals 1 and a perfect negative correlation equals -1. The eigenvalues of the factors and the (cumulative) percentage explanation of the variance are shown at the bottom of the matrix. The eigenvalue represents the “relative contribution of a factor to the explanation of the total variance in the matrix” (Cools, et al., 2012).

¹ $2 \text{ or } 2,5 * 100/\sqrt{N}$ with N= Number of respondents

Among those factors, we selected the significant ones. To be considered as significant, a factor must meet two conditions (Cools, et al., 2012): 1) its eigenvalue must be greater than one; 2) a significant factor must have at least two Q sorts that are correlated with it in a significant way. It is considered that a Q sort and a factor are correlated in a significant way if the correlation between them is superior to 0,5 and if the correlations between the Q sort and the other factors are inferior to 0,40.

On the basis of these criteria, we selected three significant factors: Factor 1, Factor 2 and Factor 3.

2.2.4.2: Factor rotation

After the PCA, the selected factors were rotated to obtain the final set of factors. Rotating a factor involves maximizing the contributions of the selected factor to the explanation of the variance. Among the two options that we had to carry out the rotation, namely the objective and the theoretical rotation, we chose the *objective rotation*, where the software “automatically” rotates the factors.

The Varimax rotation (which is the objective rotation tool integrated in the Ken-Q Analysis software) of the three factors previously selected, has led to the Factor matrix with identification of defining sorts (see Appendix). The first, second and third factors account for respectively 22%, 20% and 13% of the variance. Together, the combination of the three factors explains 55% of the variance.

For each factor obtained, the software identified the Q sorts correlated in a significant way, which are highlighted in yellow in the previous graph. The description of the profile of the participants associated with each factor is done in section 3.2.

Furthermore, based on the correlations between the factors (see Annex 4), we observe that Factor 1 is more correlated with Factor 2 than with Factor 3 and that the latter is closer to Factor 1 than to Factor 2.

The characteristics of the “ideal-typical visions” associated to these three factors are described in section 3.2.

2.3 Complementary analysis (fourth vision)

As explained in section 2.2.1, we only received two responses from business federations to the questions of our survey in the form of emails in which they described their vision of a just transition as well as the statements which they most agreed to.

As a result, well-knowing that we may miss out on another “ideal-typical vision” of “Just transition” by Belgian actors if we did not take the characteristics of the participants of the sample and the absence of Q sorts linked to business federations, we decided to analyze secondary sources (sources that are different from data collected through the online questionnaire) to identify the vision of a just transition shared by this type of actors.

These secondary sources include the two responses from the business federations as well as the results of a memorandum organized by ECORES (to be published) where nine business federations have completed an extensive survey on various issues related to their vision of a just transition, results which have been shared with us for the purpose of this study.

Based on these secondary sources, we depicted a fourth “ideal-typical vision” of a just transition, which is presented in section 3.4.

3. Results

3.1. Items with the most agreement and disagreement

Before presenting the three factors, we identify the statements on which participants most agreed or disagreed. The table below shows, for each statement, the scores attributed by the participants to each statement.

Participant	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	S7	S8	S9	S10	S11	S12	S13	S14	S15	S16	S17	S18	S19	S20	S21	S22	S23	S24	S25	S26	S27	S28	S29	S30	S31	S32	S33	S34	S35	S36	S37	S38	S39	
OT05	-1	-1	2	-1	0	3	2	2	1	-3	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	-1	-2	-1	-1	3	2	1	1	0	-3	-2	-2	1	0	-2	-2	-3	3	1	-1	1		
L62L	-2	0	3	1	0	-3	2	3	0	1	-2	0	-1	3	0	1	0	-1	-2	2	-3	0	-1	1	1	-2	-2	-1	2	-3	2	1	-1	-1	0	2	1	-1	0	
9RPO	-3	-1	-1	-1	-2	-3	-2	-1	-1	-1	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	3	-2	3	2	2	-2	-2	2	2	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	-3	1
H4VN	-1	1	0	1	3	1	3	0	-2	-3	1	-1	-1	-1	3	0	-2	-2	2	0	0	2	1	2	2	2	-2	-1	1	1	-2	0	-3	0	-3	0	-1	0	-1	
3XZL	-1	1	-1	0	-2	-3	2	3	0	0	-1	-1	-2	1	1	0	-1	-2	-3	3	-3	-1	0	2	0	0	0	1	2	1	3	2	-1	-2	0	1	1	-2	2	
UXB6	0	-1	0	0	1	1	2	1	1	-2	-1	-1	0	-1	2	-3	-2	-2	-1	1	0	0	2	3	2	1	0	-1	2	-2	1	3	-3	-2	-3	3	0	0	-1	
SVMZ	-3	3	3	3	1	-2	2	1	-1	1	-3	2	1	2	1	-1	0	0	0	0	-2	-1	1	-1	0	-2	-2	0	0	-1	-1	-1	-2	1	2	0	-3	2	0	
GCOI	-2	-3	-1	-3	0	0	-2	-3	-2	0	-2	-1	-2	-1	-1	-1	0	-1	1	-1	0	1	2	2	3	1	0	0	2	1	2	3	1	2	0	3	1	1	0	
YDM9	-2	3	2	3	-1	-2	1	3	1	0	-1	0	2	1	-2	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	-1	-1	-3	0	-3	-1	1	-2	-2	2	-1	2	-1	2	0	-3	0	
HLKO	-2	1	2	2	1	-2	3	2	-2	-1	-3	2	0	0	3	0	0	-1	0	-1	0	-1	1	3	1	-1	-3	-3	1	0	2	1	-1	0	-1	1	0	-2	-2	
7I6I	-3	2	1	2	-2	0	0	-2	-2	0	3	2	3	1	-1	2	1	-1	0	-1	1	-1	0	0	0	-3	-2	1	1	3	1	0	-1	0	-1	0	-1	0	-2	
LSJ1	-2	3	0	-1	2	-3	2	3	-1	3	-1	2	2	2	-1	1	0	1	1	-1	-2	0	0	-1	-2	-2	-3	-2	-1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	-3	1	
ZLX4	-1	-1	1	0	0	0	2	0	-3	-2	-1	2	0	2	2	-1	1	0	1	-1	-2	3	2	1	3	1	-3	-1	0	0	-2	1	-1	-2	-3	0	1	-2	3	
ZGOM	-3	-1	1	2	-2	-1	1	-1	1	0	0	0	2	-1	0	0	0	-1	2	0	-1	-2	1	1	0	-2	-1	3	-3	1	-1	0	2	2	3	2	-3	-2	-3	
EGSJ	-1	0	-1	-3	1	1	1	0	-2	-2	2	2	2	3	-1	-2	0	-1	-1	0	1	-1	1	1	1	0	0	2	3	-1	2	0	0	0	-3	-3	-2	3		
SKEO	-2	1	-3	-3	1	1	-1	-1	-1	1	0	1	2	2	2	3	1	-1	3	0	-2	0	-1	0	-2	0	-3	0	-2	0	0	-1	2	-1	3	1	0	-2	2	
HOB6	-3	0	3	0	-1	-2	3	0	0	-2	0	-2	0	0	1	0	0	2	-1	-2	1	3	2	2	1	-3	-2	2	1	2	1	1	-1	-1	-1	1	-1	-3	-1	
3BXQ	-3	0	2	-1	2	-2	1	1	2	-3	-2	0	-2	0	3	-1	-1	-1	0	1	1	1	1	2	-1	0	-2	-1	3	-1	1	0	0	-3	3	0	-2	2		
EVJ1	-3	1	1	1	0	-3	0	0	-1	0	0	0	-2	2	-1	0	2	0	3	-1	-1	2	1	1	-1	-1	-2	-2	1	-2	-1	-2	2	0	1	3	2	-3	3	
M32K	-1	1	1	0	0	-1	3	2	0	0	1	-1	0	-1	1	-2	-1	-3	0	0	0	2	2	3	2	-1	-3	-2	1	1	3	0	-2	1	-2	2	-1	-3	-2	
438B	-1	1	1	0	0	-2	2	3	1	-1	-1	2	-1	-3	-2	-2	0	0	3	0	-2	1	1	2	0	-1	-1	-1	2	1	1	0	3	0	-3	0	-2	-3	2	
5WAI	-3	-2	-2	-2	-1	-3	-1	-1	3	-2	0	0	0	2	1	2	1	1	1	0	-1	1	-1	0	0	0	-3	0	-1	3	3	2	0	2	-2	2	1	-1	1	
ZA7P	-1	1	3	3	2	-2	2	2	-3	-2	3	1	1	1	0	0	-1	2	1	-1	1	0	-1	-1	-2	-3	-3	1	-1	0	0	0	0	0	-2	0	-1	-2	0	
I1JO	-1	-1	1	-1	-3	-2	0	2	0	0	-1	3	0	2	0	2	2	2	1	-1	-1	3	-2	1	-2	-2	-1	-2	1	-3	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	-3	3	
UN3V	-2	2	2	2	-2	-3	0	0	1	-3	-2	3	1	2	0	0	1	0	3	-1	-1	-1	-1	0	1	0	-2	-1	3	-1	1	0	0	-1	-2	2	1	-3	1	
6RLN	-3	-3	-3	-2	-1	-2	-1	-1	-1	0	0	-2	1	0	1	-1	-1	2	1	2	-1	2	0	1	-1	3	0	0	1	1	1	2	0	3	2	0	-2	3		
AFPF	-3	0	-2	-1	0	-3	0	3	0	0	-2	-1	-1	0	0	3	-1	1	1	1	-2	3	-1	1	2	1	-3	-2	0	-1	2	2	1	0	2	-1	-2	1		
EBWF	-2	2	2	-1	-3	0	-1	-1	0	2	1	3	-3	2	-1	0	3	-1	1	1	-2	-2	1	0	-1	0	-1	-2	0	0	1	0	-3	1	2	1	0	3		
WZ2G	-2	2	3	3	2	1	3	2	-1	-2	-1	1	1	0	2	-1	-2	-1	0	-1	-1	1	2	1	1	-2	-3	-1	0	-2	0	1	0	0	-3	0	0	-3	0	
Total Score	-57	11	20	3	-4	-39	28	26	-9	-22	-24	19	-5	25	19	-1	0	-7	13	2	-22	27	2	33	10	-6	-56	-32	28	-5	22	21	-4	-7	-20	41	5	-58	23	

Table 6 – Scores of the participants for each statements and total score of each statement

However, it is important to take into consideration that lower scores do not necessarily imply that the participants disagree with the statements, as the guideline was to rank the statements according to how representative they are of the participant’s vision of a just transition. This difference of interpretation is highlighted by some participants in the Conclutory Questionnaire when asked why they strongly agreed or disagreed with some of the statements, as the following text extracts show:

- “I strongly (dis)agree not necessary (sic.) because these items are the most important or unimportant, but because I see them as essentiel (sic.) or non-essentiel (sic.) to “just transition” as we define it.”
- “C’était très difficile de faire un choix, car j’étais d’accord avec plus de 30 déclarations.”
- “Certains statements négatifs sont trop généraux ou moins prioritaires. Cela ne signifie pas forcément que je suis en désaccord total.”

The statements which the participants most agreed on:

The table below shows the statements which the participants most agreed on as representative of their vision of a just transition. The statements in bold are those which receive high scores in all three factors and which are therefore the subject of a consensus (see section 3.3).

Number	Statement	Score
36	Just transition requires meaningful participation, including that of vulnerable groups. Meaningful participation implies involvement that affords some degree of influence in the decision-making process.	+ 41
24	Just transition requires investing in reskilling workers	+33
29	Just transition requires making sustainable alternatives accessible to disadvantaged social groups	+28
7	Just transition should target vulnerable workers (ex: fossil fuel industries workers)	+28
22	Just transition requires phasing-out, as of now, industries, technologies, business models and practices that raise systemic sustainability issues (ex.: fossil fuel extraction, polluting vehicles...)	+27
8	Just transition should target vulnerable social groups (ex.: low-income households, people with health concerns, people living in rural areas, women, elderly people...)	+26
14	The “just” in “just transition” should mean ensuring access to fundamental rights for all	+25

Table 7 – Statements with the highest total score

The statement which received the highest score is the Statement 36, with six participants who ranked it in the highest column (+3) and eleven participants in the second highest column (+2) and only one participant who “disagreed” with it (-3).

*Just transition requires **meaningful participation**, including that of vulnerable groups. Meaningful participation implies involvement that affords some degree of influence in the decision-making process.*

The statement which received the second highest score is the statement 24, with five participants who ranked it in the highest column (+3) and only three participants who ranked it with a -1 score:

The statements which the participants most disagreed on:

The table below shows the statements which the participants found least representative of their vision of a just transition. The statements in bold are those which receive low scores in all three factors (see section 3.3)

Number	Statement	Score
38	Just transition should be achieved within the existing political and economic systems	-58
1	Only the justice issues associated to the climate problem should be considered as the scope of just transition	-57
27	Just transition requires ensuring the competitiveness of Belgian companies at the European and/or global levels	-56
6	Just transition should target vulnerable companies (ex.: fossil fuel industries)	-39

28	Just transition requires ensuring the security of supply in terms of energy and materials	-32
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Table 8 – Statements with the lowest total scores

The statements which received the lowest scores are the statements 1, 27 and 38 :

- *Statement 1: Only the justice issues associated to the climate problem should be considered as the scope of just transition.* No participants gave a positive score to this statement. It is interesting to compare the score of this statement with the much higher score of the statement 2(+9): *The justice issues associated to the climate problem, but also to other ecological issues (ex.: biodiversity loss, pollution...) should be considered within the scope of just transition*
- *Statement 27: Just transition requires ensuring the competitiveness of Belgian companies at the European and/or global levels.* No participant gave a positive score to this statement . However, it is worth noting that this statement is put forward by the respondents of business federations as most representative of their vision of a just transition. (see section 3.5).
- *Statement 38: Just transition should be achieved within the existing political and economic systems.* Only one participant gave a positive score to this statement (+1). It is interesting to compare the score of this statement with the much higher score of the statement 39 (+19): *Just transition requires to overhaul the existing political and/or economic systems* (see section 3.3).

3.2 Description of each factor

The presentation of the main features of each factor focuses on the statements which distinguish it from the other factors as well as on the statements which got an extreme score (-3 or +3). We have assigned a name to each factor with the aim of highlighting the emblematic characteristics of each factor:

- A “**Holistic vision**” of a just transition for Factor 1
- A “**Workers-centered vision**” of a just transition for Factor 2
- A “**Social-ecological state vision**” of a just transition for Factor 3

3.2.1 Factor 1: A “holistic vision” of just transition

Participants associated with the first factor are in favour of an overhaul of the existing political and economic system to mitigate environmental degradations while reducing existing inequalities and guaranteeing access to fundamental rights for all. This is expressed in some of the participants responses:

- *“De rechtvaardige transitie gaat over een transitie naar een sociaal, ecologisch, en economisch rechtvaardige samenleving. Een transitie waar iedereen betrokken wordt, en de kosten en baten op een rechtvaardige manier verdeeld worden.”*

- *“Une transition écologique (respect des limites planétaires) qui intègre toutes les catégories de population (tous les pays, les plus démunis, ...) dont la participation est de toute façon nécessaire à la transition.”*

Moreover, they accord great importance to the statements linked to the questions of the scope of the just transition and argue that justice issues linked to the distribution of costs and benefits of the ecological transition as well as justice issues linked to the distribution of impacts of the transition should be considered within the scope of a just transition. This scope and the measures linked to just transition should deal with all ecological issues and not only to the ones related to climate issues. We chose the name **“Holistic vision of a just transition”** to describe the tendency of these participants to consider the interconnectedness of the issues related to just transition, or, as one of the respondents put it: *“the willingness to think in a global and intergenerational perspective”*

3.2.1.1 Q sorts associated with factor 1

Eleven Q sorts are significantly correlated with factor 1. Among the participants associated with this factor, we find:

- **6 out of the 14** of the participants who work in an **administration or a public organization**. They work in the fields of Sustainable Development, Climate mitigation and adaptation, Fight against poverty and environmental policy
- **2 out of the 2** people who are active in a **citizen’s movement**. They work in the fields of climate justice and sustainable consumption
- **2 out of the 5** people who work for an **NGO**. They work in the fields of environmental protection and just transition
- **1 out of the 2** people who work for **another kind of organization**. He or she works in the field of circular economy

The table showing these Q sorts and their respective weight in the construction of the factor can be found in Annex 4

3.2.1.2 Composite Q sort of factor 1

The table below shows the composite Q sort for factor 1, which is the average ranking of the statements of the participants associated with the factor.

Composite Q sort for Factor 1

-3	-2	-1	0	1	2	3
Just transition requires ensuring the competitiveness of	Just transition requires investing in the research and development of	Just transition should target vulnerable generations (ex.: future)	Just transition requires phasing-out, as of now, industries, technologies,	Just transition requires to overhaul the existing political and/or economic	Just transition requires meaningful participation, including that of	The "just" in "just transition" should mean ensuring access to
Just transition should target vulnerable companies (ex.: fossil)	Just transition requires taxing large companies more and to redistribute	The "just" in "just transition" should mean ensuring quality and	Just transition requires developing a fair ecological taxation	Just transition requires making sustainable alternatives accessible	The justice issues associated to the climate problem, but also to	Justice in the distribution of cost and benefits of ecological
Just transition should be achieved within the existing political and	The "just" in "just transition" should mean not increasing existing	Just transition requires compensating for the ecological loss and	Just transition requires investing in reskilling workers	Just transition requires prioritizing ecological and/or social objectives	Just transition should target vulnerable social groups (ex.: low-income)	The "just" in "just transition" should mean reducing existing
	Just transition requires ensuring the security of supply in terms of energy	Just transition should target vulnerable territories (ex.: regions)	The "just" in "just transition" should mean tackling systemic forms	The "just" in "just transition" should mean reducing existing power	Justice in the distribution of the impacts (ex.: heat waves,	
	Only the justice issues associated to the climate problem should be	Just transition involves compensating workers affected by closures or	Just transition requires developing a social security that recognizes	The "just" in "just transition" should mean eradicating poverty	Just transition should target vulnerable workers (ex.: fossil fuel	
		Just transition requires investing in sustainable and job-rich sectors	Just transition requires promoting sustainable social innovations based	Just transition requires tackling existing unequal power relations that		
		Just transition requires investing in the diversification of local	Just transition should target vulnerable non-humans (ex.: animals,	The "just" in "just transition" should mean deepening and reinforcing		
			Just transition requires developing rights for non-human (animals,			
			Just transition requires assisting the recovery of ecosystems that has been			

Illustration 2 – Composite Q sort for Factor 1

3.2.1.3 Distinguishing statements of factor 1

The following table shows the distinguishing statements of factors 1, namely the statements with the highest “distance” between factor 1 and the other factors. The “distance” in this case is the difference of the average scores of the statements between one of the factors and the other factors for each statement. For instance, the distance for statement 14 between factor 1 and the other factors is equal to $(1,62 - (-0,28)) + 1,62 - 0,40$.

Statement	Statement	factor1 Q-5	factor1 Z-s	factor2 Q-5	factor1 Z-s	factor3 Q-5	factor3 Z-sc
The “just” in “just transition” should mean ensuring access to fundamental rights	14	3	1,62	-1	-0,28	0	0,404
The “just” in “just transition” should mean reducing existing inequalities	12	3	1,45	0	-0,04	0	-0,192
The justice issues associated to the climate problem, but also to other ecological	2	2	1,36	1	0,22	-3	-1,535
Justice in the distribution of the impacts (ex.: heat waves, floodings...) of ecologic	4	2	1,18	1	0,38	-2	-1,345
Just transition should be achieved within the existing political and economic syst	38	-3	-2,14	-2	-1,25	-2	-1,251

Table 9 – Distinguishing statements of factor 1

The main distinguishing statements of Factor 1 are also those which were ranked highest in the typical Q sort. Both statements 12 and 14 about the meaning of “Just in “Just transition received an extreme positive score in factor 1 and a neutral score in the other factors:

- *Statement 12: The “just” in “just transition” should mean reducing existing inequalities*
- *Statement 14: The “just” in “just transition” should mean ensuring access to fundamental rights for all*

Moreover, the typical Q sort of Factor 1 highlights the importance accorded to the question of the scope of the just transition. Indeed, the statements 2,3 and 4 are ranked at +3 or +2 in this factor and receive a neutral or negative score in the other factors:

- *Statement 2: The justice issues associated to the climate problem, but also to other ecological issues (ex.: biodiversity loss, pollution...) should be considered within the scope of just transition*

- *Statement 3: Justice in the distribution of cost and benefits of ecological transitions policies (ex.: carbon tax, energy subsidies...) should be considered within the scope of just transition*
- *Statement 4: Justice in the distribution of the impacts (ex.: heat waves, floodings...) of ecological problems should be considered within the scope of just transition*

It is also worth noting that the Statement 38 receives even lower scores in Factor 1 than in the other factors; meaning that the “Ideal-typical vision” of a “Systemic vision of a just transition” is the one which disagrees the most with the statement that *“Just transition should be achieved within the existing political and economic system”*.

3.2.2 Factor 2: A “workers-centered vision” of just transition

Participants associated with the second factor stress the importance of work-related issues and find other non-work related issues less relevant when discussing just transitions. They equate “just transition” with *“The **just transition of the workforce, and the creation of decent work and quality jobs in relation to the transition to a climate neutral and climate resilient society, taking into account and developing policies towards ensuring that employment impacts (positive and negative) of the climate transition are an integral part of policy making.**”*

As stated by one of the participants, many respondents associated with this factor are *“convinced that the **just transition is in the first place about workers' rights and addressing job losses and transformations as a result of the transition on the one hand and the upskilling and reskilling of workers on the other hand**”* and that *“Une **attention particulière doit être accordée au travail sous toutes ses facettes** (emploi, conditions de travail, protection sociale, formations,...).”*

The just transition is justified because it is “indispensable à la préservation de l'emploi et pour éviter la dégradation de la situation sociale.” (“There is no job on a dead planet”) and because *“il est nécessaire de garantir les droits et les moyens de subsistance de ces travailleurs et des populations en général.*

They agree that *“the just transition should be national and global”* but argue that it *“should also first focus on workers and emitting industries”* and that a particular attention should be accorded to *“upskilling and reskilling workers in order to make sure that no one is left behind and has quality and decent jobs as a result of the transition”*.

For all these reasons, we decided to name this second factor a “workers-centered” vision.

3.2.2.1 Q sorts associated with factor 2

Nine Q sorts are significantly correlated with the Factor 2. Among the participants associated with this factor, we find:

- **4 out of the 6** participants who work for a **trade union**
- **4 out of 14** of the participants who work in an **administration or a public organization**. They work in the fields of Tax and environmental policy, Climate policy, and sustainable development

- **1 out of the 5** people who work for an **NGO**. He or she works in the field of climate justice.

The table showing these Q sorts and their respective weight in the construction of the factor can be found in Annex 4

3.2.2.2 Composite Q sort of factor 2

The table below shows the composite Q sort for factor 2, which is the average ranking of the statements of the participants associated with the factor.

Composite Q sort for Factor 2						
-3	-2	-1	0	1	2	3
Just transition should target vulnerable non-humans (ex.: animals,	Just transition requires ensuring the security of supply in terms of energy	The "just" in "just transition" should mean ensuring access to	Just transition should target vulnerable companies (ex.: fossil	Just transition requires making sustainable alternatives accessible	Just transition involves compensating workers affected by closures or	Just transition should target vulnerable workers (ex.: fossil fuel
Just transition requires ensuring the competitiveness of	Only the justice issues associated to the climate problem should be	Just transition requires to overhaul the existing political and/or economic	The "just" in "just transition" should mean reducing existing	Just transition should target vulnerable social groups (ex.: low-income	Just transition requires meaningful participation, including that of	Just transition requires investing in reskilling workers
Just transition requires developing rights for non-human (animals,	The "just" in "just transition" should mean deepening and reinforcing	Just transition requires taxing large companies more and to redistribute	Just transition requires prioritizing ecological and/or social objectives	Just transition should target vulnerable territories (ex.: regions	Just transition requires investing in sustainable and job-rich sectors	The "just" in "just transition" should mean ensuring quality and
	Just transition should be achieved within the existing political and	Just transition requires compensating for the ecological loss and	Just transition requires investing in the diversification of local	Just transition requires developing a social security that recognizes	Just transition requires phasing-out, as of now, industries, technologies,	
	Just transition requires assisting the recovery of ecosystems that has been	The "just" in "just transition" should mean not increasing existing	Just transition requires tackling existing unequal power relations that	Just transition requires developing a fair ecological taxation	Justice in the distribution of cost and benefits of ecological	
		The "just" in "just transition" should mean reducing existing power	Just transition requires investing in the research and development of	Justice in the distribution of the impacts (ex.: heat waves,		
		The "just" in "just transition" should mean tackling systemic forms	Just transition requires promoting sustainable social innovations based	The justice issues associated to the climate problem, but also to		
			Just transition should target vulnerable generations (ex.: future			
			The "just" in "just transition" should mean eradicating poverty			

Illustration 3 – Composite Q sort for Factor 2

3.2.2.3 Distinguishing statements of factor 2

The following table shows the distinguishing statements of factor 2.

Statement	Statement	factor2 Q ₂₋₅	factor2 Z ₂₋₅	factor1 Q ₂₋₅	factor1 Z ₂₋₅	factor3 Q ₂₋₅	factor3 Z ₂₋₅
Just transition should target vulnerable workers (ex.: fossil fuel industries workers)	7	3	1,94	2	0,822	-2	-1,206
Just transition requires investing in reskilling workers	24	3	1,68	0	0,131	2	1,07
The "just" in "just transition" should mean ensuring quality and decent jobs for all	15	3	1,58	-1	-0,177	0	0,012
Just transition involves compensating workers affected by closures or downsizing of industries	23	2	1,33	-1	-0,647	-1	-0,333
Just transition requires investing in sustainable and job-rich sectors	25	2	1,1	-1	-0,702	0	0,536
The "just" in "just transition" should mean deepening and reinforcing democracy	18	-2	-1,1	1	0,236	1	0,663
Just transition requires assisting the recovery of ecosystems that has been degraded, damaged	33	-2	-1,33	0	-0,129	2	1,009
Just transition should target vulnerable non-humans (ex.: animals, plants...)	10	-3	-1,45	0	-0,024	-1	-0,671
Just transition requires developing rights for non-human (animals, plants...)	35	-3	-2,02	0	-0,117	1	0,782

Table 10 – Distinguishing statements of factor 2

The main distinguishing statements of Factor 2 are also those which were ranked highest in the typical Q sort. The following five statements, which are linked to workers, employment and company-related issues, both received the most positive scores in Factor 2 and neutral or negative scores in the other factors:

- Statement 7: Just transition should target vulnerable workers (ex: fossil fuel industries workers)
- Statement 24: Just transition requires investing in reskilling workers
- Statement 15: The “just” in “just transition” should mean ensuring quality and decent jobs for all
- Statement 23: Just transition involves compensating workers affected by closures or downsizing of industries
- Statement 25: Just transition requires investing in sustainable and job-rich sectors

It is also worth noting that some statements not linked to work-related issues and which could be linked to a “holistic” vision of a just transition receive the lowest rankings in Factor 2 while getting neutral or positive ranks in the other factors, such as:

- Statement 15: The “just” in “just transition” should mean tackling systemic forms of oppression associated to race, gender, class and/or species
- Statement 18: The “just” in “just transition” should mean deepening and reinforcing democracy
- Statement 33: Just transition requires assisting the recovery of ecosystems that has been degraded, damaged, or destroyed people in Belgium and/or elsewhere in the world
- Statement 35: Just transition requires developing rights for non-human (animals, plants...)

As one of the participants stressed it, for respondents associated with this factor, ***“The JT process needs a particular focus instead of being a forum for larger debate about other societal challenges, risking dilution instead of action oriented initiatives”.***

3.2.3 Factor 3: A “Social-ecological state” vision of a just transition

Participants associated with the third factor stress the importance of the action of the state (taxation, investment, social security) in ensuring a “just transition” and in *“Helping those who cannot help themselves.”*

The focus is put on ***“Promouvoir et instaurer des systèmes de protection sociale adéquats garantissant les soins de santé, la sécurité de revenu et des services sociaux conformément aux normes internationales du travail”*** and on ***“ les garanties de sécurité sociale”***.

It is worth noting that the statements linked to the scope of the just transition in terms of justice principles and the statements related to the question on who or what should a just transition target receive the lowest rankings, as discussed in section 3.2.3.3.

We decided to name this factor a “Social-ecological state” vision of a just transition because the issues of statement 32 (*developing a social security that recognizes ecological transitions and environmental degradation as social risks that need to be mutualized*) and statement 30 (*taxing large companies more and to redistribute the benefit to households*) correspond to the vision of Eloi Laurent of setting up a social-ecological state that “recognizes the ecological crises and environmental degradation as

social risks to be mutualized” to attenuate the inequality issues resulting from it (Laurent, 2020, pp. 130-131).

3.2.3.1 Q sorts associated with factor 3

Five Q sorts are significantly correlated with the Factor 3.

Among the participants associated with this factor, we find:

- **3 out of 14** of the participants who work in an **administration or a public organization**. They work in the fields of Labour Market, Social protection and social energy.
- **1** out of the 5 people who work for an **NGO**
- **1** of the participants who works for **another kind of organization**

The table showing these Q sorts and their respective weight in the construction of the factor can be found in Annex 4

It is important to take into consideration that this factor is associated with only five Q sorts when analyzing the results linked to this vision and when comparing them with the other factors.

3.2.3.2 Composite Q sort of factor 3

The table below shows the composite Q sort for factor 3, which is the average ranking of the statements of the participants associated with the factor.

Composite Q sort for Factor 3						
-3	-2	-1	0	1	2	3
The justice issues associated to the climate problem, but also to	Just transition requires ensuring the competitiveness of	Just transition involves compensating workers affected by closures or	Just transition requires investing in sustainable and job-rich sectors	Just transition requires taxing large companies more and to redistribute	Just transition requires developing a fair ecological taxation	Just transition requires phasing-out, as of now, industries, technologies,
Just transition should target vulnerable companies (ex.: fossil	Just transition should target vulnerable workers (ex.: fossil fuel	Just transition requires ensuring the security of supply in terms of energy	Just transition requires making sustainable alternatives accessible	Just transition requires developing rights for non-human (animals,	Just transition requires to overhaul the existing political and/or economic	Just transition requires meaningful participation, including that of
Only the justice issues associated to the climate problem should be	Just transition should be achieved within the existing political and	The "just" in "just transition" should mean not increasing existing	The "just" in "just transition" should mean ensuring access to	Just transition requires compensating for the ecological loss and	Just transition requires developing a social security that recognizes	Just transition requires investing in the diversification of local
	Justice in the distribution of the impacts (ex.: heat waves,	Just transition should target vulnerable social groups (ex.: low-income	Just transition requires tackling existing unequal power relations that	The "just" in "just transition" should mean tackling systemic forms	Just transition requires investing in reskilling workers	
	Justice in the distribution of cost and benefits of ecological	Just transition should target vulnerable non-humans (ex.: animals,	The "just" in "just transition" should mean ensuring quality and	The "just" in "just transition" should mean deepening and reinforcing	Just transition requires assisting the recovery of ecosystems that has been	
		Just transition should target vulnerable territories (ex.: regions	Just transition requires investing in the research and development of	Just transition requires prioritizing ecological and/or social objectives		
		The "just" in "just transition" should mean eradicating poverty	The "just" in "just transition" should mean reducing existing	Just transition requires promoting sustainable social innovations based		
			The "just" in "just transition" should mean reducing existing power			
			Just transition should target vulnerable generations (ex.: future			

Illustration 4 – Composite Q sort for Factor 3

3.2.3.3 Distinguishing statements of factor 3

The following table shows the distinguishing statements of factor 3.

Statement	Statement	factor3 Q-5	factor3 Z-s	factor1 Q-5	factor1 Z-s	factor2 Q-5	factor2 Z-s
Just transition requires investing in the diversification of local economies	26	3	1,36	-1	-0,74	0	-0,11
Just transition requires developing a fair ecological taxation	31	2	1,33	0	0,16	1	0,55
Just transition requires investing in reskilling workers	24	2	1,07	0	0,13	3	1,68
Just transition requires assisting the recovery of ecosystems that has been degraded	33	2	1,01	0	-0,13	-2	-1,33
Just transition requires taxing large companies more and to redistribute the benefit to households	30	1	0,96	-2	-0,86	-1	-0,42
Justice in the distribution of the impacts (ex.: heat waves, floodings...) of ecological transitions policies (ex.: carbon tax, etc.)	4	-2	-1,35	2	1,18	1	0,38
Justice in the distribution of cost and benefits of ecological transitions policies (ex.: carbon tax, etc.)	3	-2	-1,52	3	1,46	2	1,05
The justice issues associated to the climate problem, but also to other ecological issues	2	-3	-1,54	2	1,36	1	0,22

Table 11 – Distinguishing statements of factor 3

The main distinguishing statements of Factor 3 are also those which were ranked highest in the typical Q sort. The following four statements, which are linked to investment, social security and taxation, have high scores in factor 3 and neutral or negative scores in the other factors.

- *Statement 26: The Just transition requires investing in the diversification of local economies*
- *Statement 32 : Just transition requires developing a social security that recognizes ecological transitions and environmental degradation as social risks that need to be mutualized*
- *Statement 33: Just transition requires assisting the recovery of ecosystems that has been degraded, damaged, or destroyed people in Belgium and/or elsewhere in the world*
- *Statement 30: Just transition requires taxing large companies more and to redistribute the benefit to households*

Moreover, the statement 33 “Just transition requires assisting the recovery of ecosystems that has been degraded, damaged, or destroyed people in Belgium and/or elsewhere in the world” and the statement 7 “Just transition should target vulnerable workers (ex.: fossil fuel industries workers)” receive a -2 score and positive scores in the other factor.

It is also worth noting that some statements received the lowest rankings in Factor 2 while getting neutral or positive ranks in the other factors, such as the statements linked to the question of the scope of the just transition and the scope of the justice issues considered relevant (statements 2,3 and 4). The questions linked to who the just transition should target also received lower scores. This could be interpreted as a tendency for participants associated with Factor 3 to prioritize statements linked to pragmatic measures and not those linked with the underlying principles of these measures.

Moreover, the statement “The justice issues associated to the climate problem, but also to other ecological issues (ex.: biodiversity loss, pollution...) should be considered within the scope of just transition” receives a -3 score.

3.3 Similarities and differences between the factors

In this section, we analyze the similarities and differences between the factors by identifying the statements which are part of an “area of consensus” and the ones which are part of the “terms of the debate”.

3.3.1 Similarities between the factors: Area of consensus

The table below shows the statements with the lowest Z-score variance, namely the statements for which the average scores are the most similar between the three factors and which therefore “make consensus”.

Factor Q-sort Values for Statements sorted by Consensus vs. Disagreement					
Statement	Statement	factor 1	factor 2	factor 3	Z-Score variance
36	Just transition requires meaningful participation, including that of vulnerable groups. Meaningful participation should be ensured through the decision-making process.	2	2	3	0,005
9	Just transition should target vulnerable generations (ex.: future generations)	0	-1	0	0,005
11	The “just” in “just transition” should mean not increasing existing inequalities	-1	-2	-1	0,06
29	Just transition requires making sustainable alternatives accessible to disadvantaged social groups	1	1	0	0,061
37	Just transition requires tackling existing unequal power relations that afford varying levels of influence	0	1	0	0,067
20	Just transition requires promoting sustainable social innovations based on solidarity (ex.: car sharing)	0	0	1	0,097
21	Just transition requires investing in the research and development of sustainable technologies	0	-2	0	0,119
19	Just transition requires prioritizing ecological and/or social objectives over economic growth	0	1	1	0,126
28	Just transition requires ensuring the security of supply in terms of energy and materials	-2	-2	-1	0,134
27	Just transition requires ensuring the competitiveness of Belgian companies at the European and global level	-3	-3	-2	0,162
38	Just transition should be achieved within the existing political and economic systems	-2	-3	-2	0,177

Table 12 – Area of consensus – Statements with the lowest variance between the factors

We can observe that there is a broad consensus on statement 36 (“Just transition requires meaningful participation, including that of vulnerable groups”), which was also the statement with the higher total score (see section 3.1). Therefore, we can argue that all three “ideal-typical visions” of a just transition consider the issue of meaningful participation and of according a certain degree of influence of vulnerable groups in the decision-making process as a crucial issue. This is also expressed in the following answer by a participant: “*De transitie is enkel mogelijk met actieve medewerking van de werknemers en hun vertegenwoordigers, onder meer door hun actieve participatie in de organen van sociaal overleg (voor zover deze bestaan tenminste).*”

Furthermore, it is also worth noting that the participants agree on the low relevance of statements 11, 27, 28 and 38 in their vision of a just transition:

- Statement 11 (The “just” in “just transition” should mean not increasing existing inequalities) is considered less relevant than statement 12 (“reducing existing inequalities”) for the participants associated with the three factors, as described in section 3.3.3.3)
- Statement 27 (“ensuring the competitiveness of Belgian companies”) and statement 28 (“ensuring the security of supply in terms of energy and materials”) are considered not relevant in the vision of a just transition of the participants associated with the three factors. As described in section 3.5, we will see that this will differ significantly in the vision shared by business federations.
- Statement 38 (“Just transition should be achieved within the existing political and economic systems”) is considered less relevant than statement 39 (“ust transition requires to overhaul the existing political and/or economic systems”) for the participants associated with the three factors, as described in section 3.3.3.3)

3.3.2 Differences between the factors: Terms of the debate

The table below shows the statements with the highest Z-score variance in an ascending order, namely the statements for which the average scores are the least similar between the three factors and which therefore are part of the “terms of the debate”.

Factor Q-sort Values for Statements sorted by Consensus vs. Disagreement						
Statement	Statement	factor 1	factor 2	factor 3	Z-Score variance	
14	The “just” in “just transition” should mean ensuring access to fundamental rights for all	3	-1	0	0,617	
15	The “just” in “just transition” should mean ensuring quality and decent jobs for all	-1	3	0	0,622	
23	Just transition involves compensating workers affected by closures or downsizing of industries	-1	2	-1	0,749	
26	Just transition requires investing in the diversification of local economies	-1	0	3	0,776	
6	Just transition should target vulnerable companies (ex.: fossil fuel industries)	-3	0	-3	0,821	
33	Just transition requires assisting the recovery of ecosystems that has been degraded, damaged, or destroyed	0	-2	2	0,909	
4	Justice in the distribution of the impacts (ex.: heat waves, floodings...) of ecological problems should be considered	2	1	-2	1,108	
35	Just transition requires developing rights for non-human (animals, plants...)	0	-3	1	1,365	
2	The justice issues associated to the climate problem, but also to other ecological issues (ex.: biodiversity loss)	2	1	-3	1,414	
7	Just transition should target vulnerable workers (ex.: fossil fuel industries workers)	2	3	-2	1,699	
3	Justice in the distribution of cost and benefits of ecological transitions policies (ex.: carbon tax, energy subsidies)	3	2	-2	1,731	

Table 13 – Terms of the debate – Statements with the highest variance between the factors

Firstly, we observe that the statements linked to the scope of the just transition and the scope of the justice issues considered relevant (2,3, and 4) as well as the statements answering the question of the targets of a just transition (6 and 7) receive lower scores in factor 3 than in the other factors. However, as explained in section 3.2.3, this is linked to a tendency of participants associated with factor 3 to focus on pragmatic measures rather than on the justice principles underlying these measures.

Moreover, in line with the observations made in section 3.2.2, the statements linked to workers-related issues receive higher rankings in factor 2 than in the other factors. Indeed, the statements 15 (“ensuring quality and decent jobs for all”) and 23 (“compensating workers affected by closures or downsizing of industries”) receive a +3 and +2 score in factor 2 while receiving a neutral (0) or negative (-1) ranking in the other factors. Furthermore, it is also worth noting that statement 6, namely that the “Just transition should target vulnerable companies”) receives a neutral score (0) in factor 2 while receiving the most extreme negative score (-3) in the other factors.

Finally, the statement 14, namely that “The just in just transition should mean ensuring access to fundamental rights for all” receives the most extreme positive score in the holistic vision of a just transition (Factor 1) while receiving neutral or negative scores in the other visions (-1 for the “workers-centered vision” and 0 for the “social-ecological state vision”).

The distinction between the holistic vision’s (Factor 1) tendency to prioritize the issues of the access to fundamental rights and of reducing existing inequalities and the workers-centered vision’s (factor 2) tendency to prioritize workers-related issues is the main “dividing line” in terms of visions of a just transition, as we will discuss in section 4.

3.3.3 Comparing similar statements among the factors

In this section we will compare the average scores in the different factors of related statements.

3.3.3.1 Scope of the just transition

The table below shows the average score in the different factors as well as the total score of the statements linked to the question of which justice issues to consider.

Statement	Statement	factor 1 Z-score	factor 2 Z-score	factor 3 Z-score	Total score
Only the justice issues associated to the climate problem should be considered	1	-1,81	-1,05	-2,15	-57
The justice issues associated to the climate problem, but also to other ecological issues (ex.: biodiversity loss, pollution...)	2	1,36	0,22	-1,54	11
Justice in the distribution of cost and benefits of ecological transitions	3	1,46	1,05	-1,52	20
Justice in the distribution of the impacts (ex.: heat waves, floodings...)	4	1,18	0,38	-1,35	3

Table 14 – Score of the statements on the scope of the just transition for each factor

We can observe that the statement 2 “The justice issues associated to the climate problem, but also to other ecological issues (ex.: biodiversity loss, pollution...) should be considered within the scope of just transition” has significantly higher average scores in all three factors than the statement 1 “Only the justice issues associated to the climate problem should be considered as the scope of just transition”. There is a significant difference in the average scores of statement 2 between the “workers-centered vision”(1,36) and the “social-ecological state vision”(-1,54). Moreover, a similar observation can be made for the statements 3 and 4, which receive positive scores in the “holistic vision” and in the “workers-centered vision” but receive a negative score in the “Social-ecological state vision”. This is in line with the fact that statements linked to the scope of a just transition receive the lowest rankings in the “Social-Ecological State vision”, as discussed in section 3.2.3.

3.3.3.2 What or who should a just transition target ?

The table below shows the average score in the different factors as well as the total score of the statements linked to the question of “what or who” should a just transition target.

Statement	Statement	factor 1 Z-score	factor 2 Z-score	factor 3 Z-score	Total score
Just transition should target vulnerable territories (ex.: regions dependent on fossil fuel industries)	5	-0,33	0,84	-0,72	-4
Just transition should target vulnerable companies (ex.: fossil fuel industries)	6	-1,93	0,11	-1,67	-39
Just transition should target vulnerable workers (ex.: fossil fuel industries)	7	0,82	1,94	-1,21	28
Just transition should target vulnerable social groups (ex.: low-income people)	8	1,21	0,97	-0,59	26
Just transition should target vulnerable generations (ex.: future generations)	9	-0,14	-0,21	-0,31	-9
Just transition should target vulnerable non-humans (ex.: animals, plants)	10	-0,02	-1,45	-0,67	-22

Table 15 – Score of the statements for a just transition target for each factor

We can observe that the statements with the highest total score are the statements 7 and 8 which state that the “Just transition” should target vulnerable workers and vulnerable social groups, while the statements with the lowest total score are the statements 6 and 10 which state that the “Just transition” should target vulnerable companies and vulnerable non-humans. Moreover, the average score of the “workers-centered vision” for the statements 5,6 and 7 (about vulnerable territories, companies and workers) are higher than the average score of the other visions for these statements, which is in line with the observations made in section 3.2.2. Finally, we can observe that the average

score of the “social-ecological state vision” are significantly lower for all statements than the average score of the other visions for all statements, which is in line with the observations made in section 3.2.3.

3.3.3.3 What should a just transition mean ?

The table below shows the average score in the different factors as well as the total score of the statements linked to the question of what a just transition should mean.

Statement	Statement	factor 1 Z-score	factor 2 Z-score	factor 3 Z-score	Total score
The “just” in “just transition” should mean not increasing existing inequalities	11	-1,05	-0,51	-0,55	-24
The “just” in “just transition” should mean reducing existing inequalities	12	1,45	-0,04	-0,19	19
The “just” in “just transition” should mean eradicating poverty	13	0,5	-0,24	-0,85	-5
The “just” in “just transition” should mean ensuring access to fundamental rights	14	1,62	-0,28	0,4	25
The “just” in “just transition” should mean ensuring quality and decent jobs for all	15	-0,18	1,58	0,01	19
The “just” in “just transition” should mean tackling systemic forms of inequality	16	0,13	-0,89	0,68	-1
The “just” in “just transition” should mean reducing existing power imbalances	17	0,61	-0,84	-0,26	0
The “just” in “just transition” should mean deepening and reinforcing existing power imbalances	18	0,24	-1,1	0,66	-7

Table 16 – Score of the statements for the meaning of the just transition for each factor

We can observe that the statements with the highest total score are the statements 12, 14 and 15 which state that the “Just transition” should mean “reducing existing inequalities”, “ensuring access to fundamental rights” and “ensuring quality and decent jobs for all”, while the statement with the lowest total score is the statements 11 which state that the “Just transition” should mean “not increasing existing inequalities”. Therefore, while participants may agree with the statement 11, they find it less representative of their vision of a just transition than the statement about “reducing existing inequalities”. Moreover, we can observe that the average score of the “holistic vision” for the statements 12, 14 and 17, which are the statements about “reducing existing inequalities”, “ensuring access to fundamental rights” and “reducing existing power imbalances”, are higher than in the other visions, which is in line with the observations made in section 3.2.1 about the importance granted to reducing inequality and guaranteeing access to fundamental rights of the participants associated with the “holistic vision”. Finally, the “workers-centered vision” has a higher average score for statement 15 (“just transition should mean ensuring quality and decent jobs for all”) than the other factors, which is in line with the observations made in section 3.2.2 about the tendency of participants associated with this vision to put forward “workers-related issues”.

3.3.3.4 Achieve just transition within the system or overhaul the system ?

The table below shows the average score in the different factors as well as the total score of the statements 38 and 39 which address the issue of whether the just transition should be achieved within the existing political and economic system or whether it requires to overhaul the current system.

Statement	Statement	factor 1	factor 2	factor 3	Total score
		Z-score	Z-score	Z-score	
Just transition should be achieved within the existing political and economic system	38	-2,14	-1,25	-1,25	-58
Just transition requires to overhaul the existing political and/or economic system	39	0,78	-0,3	1,21	23

Table 17 – Score of the statements 38 and 39 between the factors

We can observe that both the average scores of each vision and the total score of statement 39 are higher than the ones of statement 38, meaning that most participants rather think that a “just transition requires to overhaul the existing political and/or economic system” than that it “should be achieved within the existing political and economic system”. Moreover, we can observe that the average score of the “holistic vision” for statement 38 is significantly higher than the one of the other factors, and this extremely low average score (-2,14) can be interpreted as a tendency for participants associated with the holistic vision to be even more convinced than the other participants that a just transition cannot be achieved within the current system. Finally, it is also worth noting that participants associated with the “workers-centered vision” have a lower average score for statement 39 than the other factors, which means that they are on average less convinced that a radical change of the system is needed.

3.4. A “pragmatic business-centered vision” of just transition

As explained in section 2.3, we decided to analyze secondary sources to identify the vision of a just transition shared by business federations.

Based on these secondary sources, we identified and described a fourth “ideal-typical vision” of a just transition. In this section, we describe this fourth vision (3.4.1) and identify the similarities and differences between this fourth vision and the other three factors (3.4.2).

3.4.1 Description of the fourth “ideal-typical vision”

The statements put forward by business federations in their responses are:

- Statement 7: Just transition should **target vulnerable workers** (ex.: fossil fuel industries workers)
- Statement 24: Just transition **requires investing in reskilling workers**
- Statement 27: Just **transition requires ensuring the competitiveness of Belgian companies** at the European and/or global levels
- Statement 28: Just transition requires **ensuring the security of supply** in terms of energy and materials
- Statement 21: Just transition requires **investing in the research and development of sustainable technologies**

The statements linked to ensuring the competitiveness of Belgian companies (27) and the security of supply (28) are essential in the vision shared by business federations. Indeed, in the response to the survey received by an employers’ federation, these two issues are among the three key points of their definition of a just transition:

“La transition juste fait dans un premier temps référence à la transition environnementale, c’est-à-dire une transformation vers une société :

- **bas carbone**, neutre climatiquement en 2050, sans pollution et soucieuse et protectrice de la biodiversité,
- assurant la **sécurité d’approvisionnement** énergétique et en matières/matériaux et
- offrant un cadre **compétitif** aux entreprises (level playing field). “

Indeed, as identified in the conclusions of the memorandum of ECORES, all business federations are conscious of the risks and decline in productivity linked to climate change and therefore consider the issue of competitiveness as central in their conception of just transition, which could also be described as “ensuring a level-playing field” for Belgian companies on the European and global level.

Furthermore, in the response we received to our survey, they state that “*Cette transition nécessite une vision partagée, mobilisatrice, cohérente avec les objectifs à long terme en matière d’innovation et maximisant les opportunités (de développement économique et d’implication des citoyens).*”, which is coherent with the fact that they put forward the statement 21, namely that “Just transition requires investing in the research and development of sustainable technologies.”

The measure linked to statement 24, namely that “Just transition **requires investing in reskilling workers**” is also explicitly formulated as one of the key issues of a just transition: “ *La reconversion de travailleurs d’industries en déclin en est un des enjeux, tout comme l’enseignement, qui se doit d’être en phase avec la transition (ses besoins, …).*” This is also linked to the statement that just transition should “target vulnerable workers” (statement 7) and to the fact that business federations also plead for a preventive and proactive approach in terms of anticipating societal changes linked to the labour market and accompanying affected workers and companies: “*Une telle vision [de la transition juste] entend éviter le retrait de personnes du marché du travail lorsque leur emploi disparaît ou évolue. Cela nécessite une approche préventive et proactive. Le volet préventif de cette vision gravite autour de l’anticipation de l’évolution de la société en cartographiant cette dernière [...]. Le volet proactif de cet objectif touche à l’accompagnement et au soutien des personnes dans l’adaptation de leurs profils et de leurs compétences et à l’offre de mesures et d’un soutien approprié aux entreprises les plus touchées par la transition.*”

3.4.2 Similarities and differences with the other factors

The table below shows the average scores and the total score of the statements put forward by business federations (see previous section) in the other factors.

Statement	Statement	factor1 Z-s	factor2 Z-s	factor3 Z-s	Total score
Just transition should target vulnerable workers (ex.: fossil fuel industries workers)	7	0,82	1,94	-1,21	28
Just transition requires investing in reskilling workers	24	0,13	1,68	1,07	33
Just transition requires ensuring the competitiveness of Belgian companies at the European and global level	27	-1,86	-1,72	-0,94	-56
Just transition requires investing in the research and development of sustainable technologies	21	-0,85	-0,16	-0,078	-22
Just transition requires ensuring the security of supply in terms of energy and materials	28	-1,409	-1,015	-0,513	-32

Table 18 – Score of the statements put forward by business federations in the other factors

We can observe that, on the one hand, there can be an overlap between the “company-centered vision” and the other ideal-typical visions for:

- The statement 7 (“Just transition should target vulnerable workers”), which receives high scores in factor 1 and 2 and a high total score. As explained in section 3.2.3, the fact that this statement receives a negative score in factor 3 does not necessarily mean that the participants associated with this factor disagree with the statement as these participants have a tendency to prioritize statements linked to pragmatic measures rather than statements linked to the question of who a just transition should target.
- The statement 24 (“Just transition requires investing in reskilling workers”), which receives positive or neutral average scores in the three factors as well as a high total score.

On the other hand, there is a clear dividing line between the “company-centered vision” and the other ideal-typical visions for:

- The statement 27 (“Just transition requires ensuring the competitiveness of Belgian companies at the European and/or global levels”), which receives low scores in all other factors and for its total score (-56), with *no* participant that gave a positive score to this statement.
- The statement 28 (“Just transition requires ensuring the security of supply in terms of energy and materials”), which receives low scores in the three other factors as well as a low total score (-32).

It is worth noting that the “distance” between the “company-centered vision” and the other factors for these two statements is slightly lower when comparing it only with factor 3.

Moreover, it is also interesting to analyze whether the statement which made consensus between the three factors and received the highest total score, namely statement 36 (“Just transition requires meaningful participation, including that of vulnerable groups. Meaningful participation implies involvement that affords some degree of influence in the decision-making process.”), is also part of the vision shared by business federations. As described in section 3.3.1, this statement is part of the “area of consensus” of the three factors, and is considered crucial in the vision of a just transition.

In the response to our survey by business federations, we can find the following statement: *“La transition requerra également un **rôle plus actif des citoyens**, notamment au niveau de la production d’énergie et dans leur gestion de celle-ci. La transition sera **juste** si elle intègre ces différents éléments et prend en compte l’ensemble des acteurs (dont les acteurs économiques) de la société. »*

Therefore, we can argue that, while business federations want to promote a more active role for citizens, they do not mention meaningful participation of vulnerable groups in political decision-making processes as part of their vision of a just transition. As a result, the question of whether there is an overlap or a dividing line between the “pragmatic business-centered vision” and the other visions on this issue remains open.

4. Conclusion

The 29 responses from the Q survey as well as the analysis of secondary sources have allowed us to identify four ideal-typical visions of a just transition as well as areas of convergences and of debate between these four visions:

Vision 1: “Holistic” vision of a just transition	Vision 2: “Workers-centered” vision of a just transition	Vision3: “Social-ecological state” vision of a just transition	Vision 4: “Pragmatic business-centered” vision of a just transition
Corresponds to Factor 1 of the Q survey	Corresponds to Factor 2 of the Q survey	Corresponds to Factor 3 of the Q survey	Identified through analysis of responses by business federations and secondary sources
Participants associated with this vision consider the interconnectedness of the issues related to just transition and stress the importance of simultaneously reducing environmental degradation and existing inequalities while guaranteeing access to fundamental rights for all	Participants associated with this vision stress the importance of work-related issues and argue that the just transition should first focus on the rights and conditions of workers.	Participants associated with this vision stress the importance of the action of the state in ensuring a just transition through taxation, investment and social security.	Participants associated with this vision see the just transition as a “level-playing field” for companies and stress the importance of guaranteeing the security of supply of energy and materials.

Table 19 – Summary of the four visions of a just transition identified in our analysis

As explained in section 3.3.2, the distinction between the “holistic vision” (Factor 1) and the “workers-centered vision”, namely the tendency to prioritize the issues of the access to fundamental rights and of reducing existing inequalities versus the tendency to prioritize workers-related issues is the main “dividing line” in terms of visions of a just transition. Indeed, **it raises the fundamental question of whether the just transition is a social-ecological project aimed at ensuring the transition towards a just and environmentally sustainable society or whether it is a social project aimed at “leaving no one behind” and guaranteeing the perspectives of workers and their access to decent and quality jobs as part of the ecological transition.** It is interesting to observe that this major dividing line is similar to the one found in the literature when analyzing the evolution of the debates around “just transition”, a concept which is both used as “a labor-oriented concept” as well as an “integrated framework for justice” (Wang & Lo, 2021).

Moreover, another dividing line in terms of visions of just transition is the distinction between the “company-centered vision” and the three other ideal-typical visions concerning the relevance of ensuring competitiveness of Belgian companies and their security of supply as a constitutive part of just transition. Indeed, as discussed in section 3.4.2, we found that this is a key point of the “company-centered vision”, while these issues are considered not relevant within the scope of a just transition for the other participants.

On the other hand, our study has allowed us to identify areas of convergence between these contrasting visions, which contributes to a more complex and nuanced understanding of the demarcation between the visions. Indeed, while the four visions all have salient characteristics which demarcate them from the others, areas of convergence exist for instance around the measure of “investing in reskilling workers”, with varying degrees of priority. Furthermore, there is a broad consensus on the importance of “**meaningful participation of vulnerable groups**” in the decision-making processes linked to just transition, which is the statement with the highest average score in the Q survey. However, considering that the business federations associated with the “pragmatic business-centered vision” did not mention this issue in their responses, it remains unclear whether the consensus extends to this latter vision or whether this constitutes a “dividing line” with the other visions.

Moreover, further research could be done on the “Social-ecological state vision” and on the “Company-centered vision”, as the first vision was constructed based on a relatively lower number of Q sorts while the latter was constructed following an analysis of their responses and of secondary sources. This would also allow us to study whether the shared vision of participants associated with Factor 3 corresponds to the “Social-ecological state vision” of a just transition elaborated by Eloi Laurent, and therefore whether or not we identified this vision correctly.

Finally, further qualitative studies would be needed to understand more precisely these areas of convergence and to acquire a more detailed understanding of the areas of debate around themes such as (but not limited to) the importance of meaningful participation in a just transition, the reduction of existing inequalities in a just transition or the adaptation of social security to incorporate environmental risks.

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6. Appendix

List of analyzed documents

Reference	Type of organization	Level
Accord de Paris	Public authorities	United Nations
Accord de Glasgow	Public authorities	United Nations
Solidarity and Just Transition Silesia Declaration Silesia Declaration	Public authorities	United Nations
Supporting the conditions for a just transition internationally	Public authorities	United Nations
OIT. 2015. Principes directeurs pour une transition juste vers des économies et des sociétés écologiquement durables pour tous	Trade Unions	United Nations
European Green Deal	Public authorities	Europe
European Climate Law	Public authorities	Europe
Council recommendation on ensuring a fair transition towards climate neutrality	Public authorities	Europe
European Environmental Agency. 2022. Towards 'just resilience': leaving no one behind when adapting to climate change	Public authorities	Europe
Banque Européenne d'investissement. Soutien au mécanisme pour une transition juste – Proposition globale du Groupe BEI	Public authorities	Europe
Oxfam. 2020. Confronting carbon inequality in the european union	Development NGOs	Europe
Eloi Laurent. 2020. La transition Juste	Académique	Europe
CFDD. 2020. Avis sur l'organisation d'une conférence nationale sur une transition juste vers une économie et une société écologiquement durables pour tous	Société Civile	Belgique
Resilience Management Group. Le plan 'sophia' : un plan de transition pour la belgique pour une relance durable post-covid-19	Société Civile	Belgique
Coalition Climat. 2022. Faisons de la Belgique un modèle de transition juste	Société Civile	Belgique

Coalition Climat. 2021. Mémoire pour un green new deal belge	Société Civile	Belgique
Greenpeace. Transition juste : les acquis sociaux et les luttes à venir	ONG environnement	Belgique
Oxfam. Justice Climatique.	ONG de développement	Belgique
Recommandations du Panel Citoyen Climat Wallon	Citoyens	Région Wallonne

Annex 2: Analytical framework used for the documentary analysis

Overarching questions	Dimensions
Scope of just transition	Ecological transition(s) covered
	Dimensions of transition (in-)justices considered
	Subjects of these (in-)justices
Vision of just transition	Definition of « just transition »
	Desirable future towards which « just transition » should leads our societies
Means for achieving this vision	Objectives (What ?)
	Actions (How ?)
	Actors (Who ?)
	Geographical scale (Where?)
	Temporal scale (When?)
	Procedural justice
	Reform versus Revolution
Monitoring and evaluating progress in achieving this vision	Measure
	Policy assessment

Annex 3: Interview guide

Introduction

1. Pourriez-vous **présenter** brièvement votre organisation ainsi que votre rôle au sein de celle-ci ?

Vision de la « transition juste »

1. Il existe des conceptions très variées de la transition juste. Pour vous, qu'est-ce que c'est la « **transition juste** » ?
 - a. Si pas abordé : Quelles **transitions écologiques** considérez-vous ? Ex.: Transition vers une société climatiquement neutre et/ou résiliente / Autre(s) transitions écologiques
 - b. Si pas abordé : Quelles **formes d'(in-)justices** considérez-vous ? Ex.: contribution inégale aux problèmes écologiques / Distribution inégale des impacts des problèmes écologiques / Distribution inégale des coûts et bénéfices des transitions écologiques / reconnaissance et/ou participation inégale aux processus d'élaboration de politiques et/ou des connaissances sur ces questions
 - c. Si pas abordé : Qui sont les **subjects** de ces (in-)justices. Ex. : entreprises, travailleurs, groupes sociaux (pauvres, femmes, personnes racisées...), territoires (ex.: régions dépendantes des énergies fossiles, pays du Sud...), générations, non-humains
2. Si votre **vision** idéale de la transition juste était mise en œuvre, à quoi ressemblerait le monde 1) aujourd'hui, et 2) à plus long terme ?

Concrétisation de cette vision

1. **Quoi** : Quels **objectifs** devraient être adoptés en vue d'opérationnaliser votre vision de la transition juste ? (et pourquoi ?)
2. **Comment** : Quelles **actions** devraient être mises en œuvre pour atteindre ces objectifs ? (et pourquoi ?)
 - Si pas abordé : Comment **financer** ces actions ?
3. **Qui** : Quels **acteurs** devraient 1) définir ces objectifs, 2) les traduire en actions et 3) mettre en œuvre ces actions ? i.e. : pouvoir publics, marché, société civile organisée, citoyens ordinaires, ou encore la science ? (et pourquoi ?)

- Si acteur(s) oublié(s) : quel rôle devrait jouer tel ou tel **acteur** dans votre vision de la transition juste ?
4. **Où** : A quelle **échelle géographique** ces acteurs agissent-ils? i.e.: local, régional, national, Européen ou international ? (et pourquoi ?)
 5. **Quand** : A quelle **échecance temporelle** ces actions sont-elles mises en oeuvre? (et pourquoi ?)
 6. Si pas abordé explicitement : est-ce que les **systèmes politiques et économiques actuels** permettent la concrétisation de votre vision de la transition juste ? (et pourquoi ?)
 - Si non, comment configurer ceux-ci ?

La suivi et l'évaluation des progrès dans la concrétisation de cette vision

1. Selon vous, comment effectuer le **suivi et l'évaluation des progrès** dans le cadre de la transition juste ?
2. Comment **mesurer** la transition juste ? Quels **indicateurs** utiliser ?
 - Si pas abordé : Comment et par qui ces mesures devraient-elle être produites ?
3. Comment **évaluer les politiques** de transition juste ?
 - Si pas abordé : Comment et par qui ces évaluations devraient être réalisées ?

Positionnement de cette vision dans le paysage des acteurs concernés par la transition juste en Belgique

1. Quels sont les **principaux acteurs concernés** par la transition juste en Belgique ?
2. Comment positionneriez-vous **votre vision de la transition juste** parmi celles des autres acteurs?
3. Quels sont les **points de convergence** entre votre vision et celles des autres acteurs ?
4. Quels sont les **points de divergence** entre votre vision et celles des autres acteurs ?

Conclusion

3. Souhaiteriez-vous ajouter d'autres éléments ?

Annex 4: Principal Component Analysis & Factor Rotation - Tables

Correlations between Q sorts	OT05	L62L	9RP0	H4VN	3XZL	UXB6	SVMZ	GCOI	YDM9	HLKO	7I6I	LSJ1	ZLX4	ZG0M	EGSJ	SKEO	HOB6	3BXQ	EVIJ	M32K	438B	SWAI	ZA7P	11JO	UN3V	6RLN	AFPF	EBWF	WZ2G
OT05	100	40	9	44	22	64	14	11	19	40	26	4	56	13	9	-10	36	59	19	54	23	13	38	26	29	-9	22	-4	57
L62L	40	100	11	-2	64	30	52	-4	43	56	44	43	24	64	-18	-4	37	44	39	38	20	15	48	46	45	0	47	29	43
9RP0	9	11	100	6	21	5	14	50	11	27	45	6	22	37	25	14	31	35	35	31	19	51	1	35	34	58	55	5	-5
H4VN	44	-2	6	100	1	54	10	7	3	44	3	-7	52	-11	37	-10	21	41	-1	53	16	-4	30	-28	7	-15	10	-32	54
3XZL	22	64	21	1	100	37	28	5	11	33	29	20	14	30	14	-4	28	38	11	37	26	23	9	20	23	26	39	25	15
UXB6	64	30	5	54	37	100	6	29	1	44	5	-23	32	9	11	-38	21	55	-16	57	16	-3	19	-17	13	-14	8	-19	44
SVMZ	14	52	14	10	28	6	100	-30	56	62	56	61	32	36	-4	19	31	39	50	22	25	-6	56	30	58	-5	16	36	51
GCOI	11	-4	50	7	5	29	-30	100	-31	6	-4	-26	16	10	6	-2	18	20	11	17	6	33	-33	-8	-2	44	29	0	-17
YDM9	19	43	11	3	11	1	56	-31	100	33	44	56	12	43	-15	1	23	30	44	23	32	12	59	44	54	-8	33	4	46
HLKO	40	56	27	44	33	44	62	6	33	100	56	41	43	38	0	-4	53	54	26	66	37	11	62	23	51	-17	34	-1	71
7I6I	26	44	45	3	29	5	56	-4	44	56	100	43	38	44	10	19	38	28	37	36	22	37	48	44	67	17	33	28	38
LSJ1	4	43	6	-7	20	-23	61	-26	56	41	43	100	22	20	-1	45	25	15	48	23	34	22	45	44	35	3	41	22	35
ZLX4	56	24	22	52	14	32	32	16	12	43	38	22	100	-4	32	12	38	37	38	31	30	17	37	33	42	12	25	14	56
ZG0M	13	64	37	-11	30	9	36	10	43	38	44	20	-4	100	-31	-3	16	20	41	28	-3	11	19	30	40	14	31	12	15
EGSJ	9	-18	25	37	14	11	-4	6	-15	0	10	-1	32	-31	100	18	10	13	-17	13	4	11	-9	-4	-11	21	8	-22	12
SKEO	-10	-4	14	-10	-4	-38	19	-2	1	-4	19	45	12	-3	18	100	-17	-4	36	-16	-6	31	1	28	9	44	32	31	-8
HOB6	36	37	31	21	28	21	31	18	23	53	38	25	38	16	10	-17	100	46	27	52	36	26	28	28	30	3	27	0	46
3BXQ	59	44	35	41	38	55	39	20	30	54	28	15	37	20	13	-4	46	100	42	50	47	35	56	26	49	19	39	-3	52
EVIJ	19	39	35	-1	11	-16	50	11	44	26	37	48	38	41	-17	36	27	42	100	17	39	21	37	56	55	37	42	39	26
M32K	54	38	31	53	37	57	22	17	23	66	36	23	31	28	13	-16	52	50	17	100	44	17	37	2	23	-16	32	-15	58
438B	23	20	19	16	26	16	25	6	32	37	22	34	30	-3	4	-6	36	47	39	44	100	13	52	31	46	7	40	6	44
SWAI	13	15	51	-4	23	-3	-6	33	12	11	37	22	17	11	11	31	26	35	21	17	13	100	16	33	34	50	54	12	-7
ZA7P	38	48	1	30	9	19	56	-33	59	62	48	45	37	19	-9	1	28	56	37	37	52	16	100	38	66	-21	27	-1	70
11JO	26	46	35	-28	20	-17	30	-8	44	23	44	44	33	30	-4	28	28	26	56	2	31	33	38	100	51	31	45	37	16
UN3V	29	45	34	7	23	13	58	-2	54	51	67	35	42	40	-11	9	30	49	55	23	46	34	66	51	100	5	30	31	43
6RLN	-9	0	58	-15	26	-14	-5	44	-8	-17	17	3	12	14	21	44	3	19	37	-16	7	50	-21	31	5	100	55	18	-33
AFPF	22	47	55	10	39	8	16	29	33	34	33	41	25	31	8	32	27	39	42	32	40	54	27	45	30	55	100	3	20
EBWF	-4	29	5	-32	25	-19	36	0	4	-1	28	22	14	12	-22	31	0	-3	39	-15	6	12	-1	37	31	18	3	100	-14
WZ2G	57	43	-5	54	15	44	51	-17	46	71	38	35	56	15	12	-8	46	52	26	58	44	-7	70	16	43	-33	20	-14	100

Annex 4.1 Matrix of correlations between the Q sorts

Unrotated Factor Matrix		Participant	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3	Factor 4	Factor 5	Factor 6	Factor 7	Factor 8
1	OT05		0.5639	-0.4434	0.1724	-0.0135	0.2283	-0.2599	-0.0976	-0.2481
2	L62L		0.7106	0.0741	-0.1703	-0.47	0.2215	0.1604	-0.1715	-0.1443
3	9RPO		0.4343	0.3253	0.6083	-0.0567	-0.2298	0.042	0.324	0.1507
4	H4VN		0.3138	-0.6762	0.2283	0.3419	0.0226	0.0618	0.1721	-0.2241
5	3XZL		0.4701	0.0424	0.2051	-0.3963	0.37	0.3962	-0.3858	0.1455
6	UXB6		0.3573	-0.6888	0.3	-0.2842	0.2087	-0.0513	-0.06	-0.1532
7	SVMZ		0.6737	0.1164	-0.4479	0.0614	0.2097	0.1546	0.2234	0.0575
8	GCOI		0.054	0.0395	0.7729	-0.2146	-0.0355	-0.2545	0.1694	-0.006
9	YDM9		0.6028	0.1382	-0.4418	-0.0082	-0.3514	0.0399	-0.0225	-0.1315
10	HLKO		0.7838	-0.2956	-0.0827	-0.0734	-0.0186	0.1769	0.2117	0.0734
11	7I6I		0.6996	0.2316	-0.0582	0.0205	0.0429	0.1535	0.3847	0.2359
12	LSJ1		0.5629	0.3491	-0.3682	0.2674	-0.0588	0.3216	-0.1571	-0.0358
13	ZLX4		0.5815	-0.1935	0.1919	0.4248	0.3643	-0.2349	0.1384	-0.0077
14	ZGOM		0.4727	0.2472	-0.0826	-0.6098	-0.1222	0.1228	0.3426	-0.2644
15	EGSJ		0.0549	-0.1755	0.4259	0.5429	0.1671	0.4259	0.0284	0.1614
16	SKEO		0.1196	0.5778	0.0695	0.5019	0.2023	0.1992	0.0329	-0.3438
17	HOB6		0.5904	-0.1679	0.1602	-0.0464	-0.0845	0.0092	0.0113	0.4597
18	3BXQ		0.7217	-0.2343	0.2589	-0.0262	-0.0324	-0.1805	-0.167	-0.0949
19	EVUJ		0.616	0.4476	-0.0543	0.1011	0.0054	-0.3339	0.053	-0.1815
20	M32K		0.6293	-0.4662	0.1978	-0.1248	-0.1299	0.2018	-0.0018	0.0624
21	43BB		0.5641	-0.0694	0.0154	0.1718	-0.2503	-0.2306	-0.4529	0.3131
22	5WAI		0.3695	0.3867	0.4923	0.073	-0.1889	0.0187	-0.0835	0.0485
23	ZA7P		0.7248	-0.1631	-0.4021	0.1885	-0.2024	-0.1266	-0.0889	-0.0555
24	I1JO		0.5605	0.5109	-0.0727	0.058	0.0359	-0.2123	-0.1721	0.0412
25	UN3V		0.7463	0.1817	-0.1706	0.0021	-0.033	-0.2923	0.1768	0.1377
26	6RLN		0.137	0.5987	0.6417	0.0757	0.033	0.0177	-0.062	-0.1212
27	AFPF		0.5929	0.3235	0.3916	0.0032	-0.2332	0.1823	-0.2698	-0.2484
28	E8WF		0.1918	0.52	-0.1594	-0.1079	0.617	-0.2324	-0.0083	0.1936
29	WZ2G		0.7018	-0.506	-0.2476	0.203	-0.0141	0.009	0.0172	-0.0711
Eigenvalues			8.67397986	3.96707978	3.20736661	1.96615934	1.32885049	1.27085768	1.14965347	0.99727244
% Explained Variance			30	14	11	7	5	4	4	3

Annex 4.2 Matrix crossing the 8 factors with the Q sorts of the participants:

Factor Matrix with Defining Sorts				
Flagged	Column1	Column2	Column3	Column4
Part.No.	Q sort	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3
1	ADM - OT05	0.7182	0.151	0.0753
2	OTH -L62L	0.3247	0.6527	0.0897
3	ADM -9RPO	0.171	0.1586	0.7811
4	NGO -H4VN	0.7597	-0.164	-0.0623
5	ADM - 3XZL	0.3022	0.2691	0.318
6	ADM -UXB6	0.8138	-0.1726	0.0023
7	NGO -SVMZ	0.1985	0.7825	-0.1281
8	ADM -GCOI	0.203	-0.3316	0.6714
9	ADM -YDM9	0.1412	0.7352	-0.1315
10	ADM -HLKO	0.6714	0.5076	-0.0018
11	ADM -7I6I	0.2277	0.6545	0.2574
12	NGO -LSJ1	-0.0235	0.7571	0.023
13	TRU - ZLX4	0.5443	0.26	0.2203
14	CIT -ZGOM	0.0739	0.5023	0.1832
15	TRU -EGSJ	0.2764	-0.2472	0.2788
16	ADM -SKEO	-0.3486	0.2992	0.3768
17	TRU -HOB6	0.522	0.2934	0.2092
18	ADM -3BXQ	0.6765	0.3148	0.2934
19	CIT -EVUJ	0.015	0.6808	0.3451
20	TRU -M32K	0.7812	0.1779	0.1026
21	NGO - 43BB	0.3941	0.3882	0.1317
22	ADM -5WAI	0.0556	0.194	0.6983
23	ADM -ZA7P	0.4529	0.6799	-0.2153
24	ADM -I1JO	-0.0711	0.6749	0.3463
25	ADM - UN3V	0.2643	0.7252	0.1526
26	OTH -6RLN	-0.2055	0.0332	0.8635
27	NGO - AFPF	0.211	0.3865	0.6447
28	ADM -E8WF	-0.3209	0.4445	0.179
29	TRU - WZ2G	0.7392	0.4399	-0.2645
%Explained Variance		19	22	13
Cumulative Explained Variance		19	41	54

Annex 4.3 Matrix with identification of the defining sorts for each factor (highlighted in yellow)

Factor score correlations	factor 1	factor 2	factor 3
factor 1	1	0.388	0.0841
factor 2	0.388	1	0.204
factor 3	0.0841	0.204	1

Annex 4.4 Matrix of factor scores correlations

factor 1		Sorts Weight
Q Sort	Weight	
I1JO	5.1438	
7I6I	4.75166	
L62L	4.71921	
SVMZ	8.3763	
LSJ1	7.36174	
YDM9	6.64034	
UN3V	6.3483	
EVIJ	5.26614	
ZA7P	5.24718	
ZG0M	2.78799	
E8WF	2.29891	

Annex 4.5 Matrix of the Q sorts and their respective weight in the construction of factor 1

Factor 2		Sorts Weight
Q Sort	Weight	
UXB6	10	
M32K	8.31857	
H4VN	7.45586	
WZ2G	6.76331	
OT05	6.15574	
3BXQ	5.17654	
HLKO	5.07325	
ZLX4	3.2098	
HOB6	2.97769	

Annex 4.6 Matrix of the Q sorts and their respective weight in the construction of factor 2

factor 3		Sorts Weight
Q Sort	Weight	
6RLN	10	
9RP0	5.90174	
5WAI	4.01472	
GCOI	3.60113	
AFPF	3.24999	

Annex 4.7 Matrix of the Q sorts and their respective weight in the construction of factor 3